

README file

Data Set Title: CONSOLE_WP3_Task3.3_Pan-EU survey of stakeholders_common_2022.10.31_v01.

Data Set Author/s: Oili Tarvainen, Natural Resources Institute Finland. E-mail: oili.tarvainen@luke.fi. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3965-7400>

Data Set Contributor/s: Katri Hamunen, Natural Resources Institute Finland. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2188-782X>. Mikko Kurttila, Natural Resources Institute Finland. E-mail: mikko.kurttila@luke.fi. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5290-4771>

Data Set Contact Person/s: Oili Tarvainen, Natural Resources Institute Finland. E-mail: oili.tarvainen@luke.fi. ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3965-7400>

Data Set License: this data set is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license [<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>].

Publication Year: 2022.

Project Info: **CONSOLE** (*CONtract SOLutions for Effective and lasting delivery of agri-environmental-climate public goods by EU agriculture and forestry*) funded by the European Union, Horizon 2020 Programme. Grant Agreement No. 817949; <https://console-project.eu>.

Data set contents

The data set consists of: Excel xlsx. file "CONSOLE_WP3_Task3.3_Pan-EU survey of stakeholders_common_2022.10.31_v01".

Data set documentation

Abstract

Data collected from the 14 key actor and stakeholder surveys, properly operated through data management and assembled as a coherent and cohesive database to be used by the whole Consortium.

Content of the files

The data set contains 486 records observed with respect to 67 variables. Variable coding follows the coding reported below.

File specifics

–

Notes

–

Codes of questions and answers: Data sheet

la	Variable name	Answer	Codes of Answer	Notes
Questionnaire number	quest_nr	Progressive questionnaire number	1,2,3,4,...	
Partner	partner	UNIBO	1	
		LUKE	2	
		BOKU	3	
		IAE	4	
		TI	5	
		EVENOR, ASAJA, UPM,	6	
		TRAME, INRA,	7	
		UCC	8	
		UNIPI	9	
		ZSA	10	
		VUA	11	
		SGGW	12	
		UoL	13	
Way	way	Online/web	O	
		Telephone	T	
		Postal	P	
		Face to face	F	
Interviewer Name	interviewer_name_txt	Name of the interviewer	(answer text)	Only for face to face and telephone
Date Interview	interviewer_date	[ddmm]		
Duration (minutes)	duration	as minutes		Optional
Regional level of the respondent	regional_level	National	N	
		Regional	R	
		Local	L	
BACKGROUND				
1.1 What is your background organization?	1.1_organization	a) Governmental organization, state level (e.g. ministry)	1	
		b) Governmental organization, regional or local level	2	

la	Variable name	Answer	Codes of Answer	Notes
		c) Non-governmental organization (interest group)	3	
		d) Non-profit organization (e.g. foundation, association)	4	
		e) Private company	5	
		f) Public enterprise	6	
		g) Academic (e.g. university, research institute)	7	
		h) Civil society / Private individual	8	
		i) Other, please specify	9	
		Do not answer	999	
	1.1_organization_txt	(if 1.1_organization=9)	(answer text)	
1.2 What is your special area of responsibility? (multiple answers allowed)	1.2_responsibility	a) Agriculture	1	Multiple answers separated by “;”
		b) Forestry	2	
		c) Food sector	3	
		d) Environmental protection / nature conservation	4	
		e) Water management	5	
		f) Land use policy and planning	6	
		g) Training and advice	7	
		h) Research and development	8	
		i) Public administration	9	
		j) Community development	10	
		k) Other, please specify	11	
		Do not answer	999	
	1.2_responsibility_txt	(if 1.2_responsibility=11)	(answer text)	

1a	Variable name	Answer	Codes of Answer	Notes
1.3 What is your role or areas of interest? (multiple answers allowed)	1.3_role	a) Processor of agricultural or forest products	1	Multiple answers separated by “;”
		b) Provider of information to the public	2	
		c) Provider of information/advice to farmers or forest owners	3	
		d) Regulation and enforcement	4	
		e) Equipment and/or tool provision	5	
		f) Providing finance to land managers/owners/workers	6	
		g) Providing/leasing land to land managers	7	
		h) Assistance for public funding of land management	8	
		i) Lobbying, campaigning	9	
		j) Community leader	10	
		k) Supervisory authority	11	
		l) Product certification body (e.g. organic, FSC, PEFC,...)	12	
		m) Other, please specify	13	
		Do not answer	999	
	1.3_role_txt	(if 1.3_role=13)	(answer text)	
	1.3_role_most_important	most important role	(number 1-13) OR 999=missing	
ACCEPTABILITY				

Ia	Variable name	Answer	Codes of Answer	Notes
<p>2.1 How much do you think would the following characteristics of agri-environmental contracts influence land managers' willingness to enrol to an environmental contract or programme?</p> <p>1. In the contract, land managers are free to decide about the management practices to achieve the specified environmental result</p>	2.1.1	Decreases willingness considerably	1	
		Somewhat decreases willingness	2	
		No effect on willingness	3	
		Somewhat increases willingness	4	
		Increases willingness considerably	5	
		Do not answer	999	
2. The payment gets higher the better the land managers' environmental results are	2.1.2		1-5, 999	
3. Land managers can collectively agree on environmental targets and measures at landscape-level together with other land managers	2.1.3		1-5, 999	
4. Land managers receive a common payment. They jointly agree on the distribution of the payment	2.1.4		1-5, 999	
5. Land managers sell their farm's products labelled as environmentally friendly (e.g. animal welfare products, climate friendly products) when following management measures as prescribed in a	2.1.5		1-5, 999	

Ia	Variable name	Answer	Codes of Answer	Notes
processor or retailer contract				
6. The contract is not paid by public money, instead the compensation that land managers get for environmentally friendly production is paid by buyers of the products	2.1.6		1-5, 999	
7. Land managers can lease land with a reduced rent, if they agree to follow environmental management clauses as specified in the lease contract	2.1.7		1-5, 999	
8. Land managers can do the monitoring of the environmental results themselves (e.g. counting specific plants)	2.1.8		1-5, 999	
9. The results that land managers achieve are regularly controlled by the competent authority coming onto the farm e.g. once a year	2.1.9		1-5, 999	
10. Land managers are offered free training and advice that enable them to reach the environmental targets	2.1.10		1-5, 999	
11. Land managers get a sales guarantee from a processor or retailer in return for implementing environmental measures	2.1.11		1-5, 999	
12. Land managers get environmental compensation payment on an annual basis	2.1.12		1-5, 999	
13. Land managers get half of the environmental payment at the beginning of the five-year contract period, and half at the end of it	2.1.13		1-5, 999	

la	Variable name	Answer	Codes of Answer	Notes
2.2 What contract length would land managers prefer? Agriculture	2.2_agr	a) The contract is for a one year	1	
		b) The contract has the length of a common AES (5 years)	2	
		c) The contract is for 10 years	3	
		Do not answer	999	
Forestry	2.2_for	a) The contract is for 10 years	1	
		b) The contract is for 20 years	2	
		c) The contract is for 30 years	3	
		Do not answer	999	
2.3 Result-based contract is... 1. Easy to understand.	2.3.1	Strongly disagree	1	
		Disagree	2	
		Neutral	3	
		Agree	4	
		Strongly agree	5	
		Do not answer	999	
2. Applicable for their farm	2.3.2		1-5, 999	
3. Potentially economically beneficial for their farm	2.3.3		1-5, 999	
2.4 How would you improve result-based contract described above?	2.4_txt	Improvement suggestion	(answer text)	
2.5 Collective contract is... 1. Easy to understand	2.5.1	Strongly disagree	1	
		Disagree	2	
		Neutral	3	
		Agree	4	
		Strongly agree	5	
		Do not answer	999	

la	Variable name	Answer	Codes of Answer	Notes
2. Applicable for their farm	2.5.2		1-5, 999	
3. Potentially economically beneficial for their farm	2.5.3		1-5, 999	
2.6 How would you improve collective contract described above?	2.6_txt	Improvement suggestion	(answer text)	
2.7 Value chain contract is... 1. Easy to understand	2.7.1	Strongly disagree	1	
		Disagree	2	
		Neutral	3	
		Agree	4	
		Strongly agree	5	
		Do not answer	999	
2. Applicable for their farm	2.7.2		1-5, 999	
3. Potentially economically beneficial for their farm	2.7.3		1-5, 999	
2.8 How would you improve value chain contract described above?	2.8_txt	Improvement suggestion	(answer text)	
2.9 Land tenure contract is... 1. Easy to understand	2.9.1	Strongly disagree	1	
		Disagree	2	
		Neutral	3	
		Agree	4	
		Strongly agree	5	
		Do not answer	999	
2. Applicable for their farm	2.9.2		1-5, 999	
3. Potentially economically beneficial for their farm	2.9.3		1-5, 999	
2.10 How would you improve land tenure contract described above?	2.10_txt	Improvement suggestion	(answer text)	

Ia	Variable name	Answer	Codes of Answer	Notes
2.11 ... In your opinion, how popular would they be among the land managers in your area? Please rank them. Result-based, score	2.11.1_resultbased	Most popular	1	
		Second popular	2	
		Third popular	3	
		Least popular	4	
		Do not answer	999	
Collective implementation, score	2.11.2_collective		1-4, 999	
Value chain, score	2.11.3_valuechain		1-4, 999	
Land tenure, score	2.11.4_landtenure		1-4, 999	
2.12 In your opinion, for which environmental objective provision would the four introduced contract types be the most suitable? Choose only one environmental objective in each row. Result-based	2.12.1_resultbased	Landscape and scenery	1	
		Biodiversity	2	
		Soil health and quality	3	
		Carbon storage	4	
		Water quality and quantity	5	
		Do not answer	999	
Collective implementation	2.12.2_collective		1-5, 999	
Value chain	2.12.3_valuechain		1-5, 999	
Land tenure	2.12.4_landtenure		1-5, 999	

Question	Variable name	Answer	Codes of Answer	Notes
MACRO-ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS				
1.1 3.1 What are important topics, phenomena, aspects, or trends under these six factors mentioned above that exist in the operational environment in your country or region, that would affect the adoption of result-based contract type? Please, list five of these topics in the table below.	3.1.1_topic_txt		(answer text)	
Topic 1				
Topic 2	3.1.2_topic_txt		(answer text)	
Topic 3	3.1.3_topic_txt		(answer text)	
Topic 4	3.1.4_topic_txt		(answer text)	
Topic 5	3.1.5_topic_txt		(answer text)	
1.2 3.2 Mark if these topics are promoting or hindering (+/-) the adoption of result-based contract type.	3.2.1_effect	promoting	1	
Topic 1		hindering	2	
		Do not answer	999	
Topic 2	3.2.2_effect		1, 2, 999	
Topic 3	3.2.3_effect		1, 2, 999	
Topic 4	3.2.4_effect		1, 2, 999	
Topic 5	3.2.5_effect		1, 2, 999	
1.3 3.3 Select one, most important topic that affects to the adoption of result-based contract type among the ones you listed.	3.3_most_important	topic 1	1	
		topic 2	2	
		topic 3	3	
		topic 4	4	
		topic 5	5	

Question	Variable name	Answer	Codes of Answer	Notes
3.1_factors: classification of the topics under six pre-defined factors (DONE BY THE PARTNERS)	3.1.1_factor	Political	1	
		Economic	2	
		Social	3	
		Technological	4	
		Legal	5	
		Environmental	6	
		Could not be classified	999	
	3.1.2_factor		1-6, 999	
	3.1.3_factor		1-6, 999	
	3.1.4_factor		1-6, 999	
	3.1.5_factor		1-6, 999	
1.4 3.4 Do you have any further comments e.g. about the presented contract types or their characteristics?	3.4.1_Contract_comments_txt		(answer text)	
1.5 3.4 You can also comment on this survey.	3.4.2_Survey_comments_txt		(answer text)	

Codes of questions and answers: Pestle factor codes

rowNo	Factor	Pestle class (1 political, 2 economic, 3 social, 4 technological, 5 legal, 6 environmental)	Short description
1	11	1	Political
2	101	1	Training
3	13	1	Political will
4	16	1	Bureaucracy
5	12	1	Political stability
6	102	1	Support
7	21	2	Economic

8	201	2	Remuneration
9	22	2	Funding resources
10	202	2	Financial risk
11	211	2	Guarantee
12	24	2	New earning
13	31	3	Social
14	39	3	Visibility
15	32	3	Farmers' acceptance
16	37	3	Consumers' interest
17	38	3	Co-operative willingness
18	35	3	Farmers' awareness
19	33	3	Farm(er) characteristics
20	36	3	Local context
21	41	4	Technological
22	42	4	Availability of technology
23	401	4	Suitable indicators
24	403	4	Monitoring
25	43	4	Implementation
26	411	4	Sufficient knowledge
27	413	4	Timeframe for measures
28	51	5	Legal
29	502	5	Contract characteristics
30	501	5	Understandability
31	52	5	Stability of legal frame
32	53	5	Compatibility with laws
33	512	5	Compatibility with goals
34	511	5	Achievability
35	61	6	Environmental

36	62	6	Climate change impact
37	63	6	Influence possibility
38	64	6	Environmental conditions
39	65	6	Timeframe for results
40	999	999	<i>No response or the reasoning could not be specified</i>